

than 80%. Many types of pollen strains combined the two parents' traits, with variation ranging close to that of F₂ progenies.

The stability of BB resistance and of other agricultural traits were analyzed in H₃ and H₄ (see table). In pollen plants, these were all relatively stable in different generations. In stable H₂ pollen strains, the resistance capability and character uniformities did not vary with generation advance (H₃ and H₄).

We concluded that the anther culture method effectively transfers the resistance gene. □

Stability of pollen strain resistance to bacterial blight.

Cross	Generation	Strain no.	Lesion area ^a (%)	Strain no.	Lesion area ^b (%)
Shennong 1033/Zenith	H ₂	89-3710	3.0 ± 0.2	89-3724	16.7 ± 1.6
	H ₃		2.0 ± 1.8		16.8 ± 1.4
	H ₄		2.3 ± 0.1		15.7 ± 1.4
Shennong 1033/75-34	H ₂	89-3841	4.7 ± 0.2	89-3873	14.5 ± 0.8
	H ₃		4.7 ± 0.2		14.7 ± 1.2
	H ₄		4.9 ± 0.1		15.7 ± 1.4
Shennong 1033/Java 14	H ₂	89-3753	2.9 ± 0.2	89-3924	14.0 ± 1.3
	H ₃		4.9 ± 0.1		13.3 ± 1.6
	H ₄		4.9 ± 0.1		12.8 ± 1.2
Shennong 1033/Pei Zhao 15	H ₂	89-3795	4.9 ± 0.1	89-3819	14.9 ± 1.1
	H ₃		4.9 ± 0.1		13.9 ± 1.2
	H ₄		4.9 ± 0.1		14.1 ± 1.1

^aAll values are equivalent to R (resistant). ^bAll values are equivalent to MR (moderately resistant).

Resistance to sheath blight (ShB) and brown spot (BS) in lines derived from *Oryza officinalis*

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We evaluated 87 breeding lines derived from *O. officinalis* for resistance to ShB caused by *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk, and BS caused by *Cochliobolus miyabeanus* (Ito & Kuribayashi) Drechsler ex Dastur.

In the field, one row per line and check TKM9 were transplanted at 30 × 15-cm in 3-m-long plots, in a randomized block with three replications.

We assessed ShB weekly and BS biweekly from active tillering to the milk stage, using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES). Lines completely free from ShB and BS were artificially inoculated for further evaluation.

Disease incidence was evaluated in the greenhouse by stem tape inoculation for ShB and spore suspension spray for BS, on 21 seedlings/line. Actively tillering plants were inoculated with 20-d-old ShB pathogen cultured on autoclaved rice stem pieces, inserted into the sheaths, 5 cm above the water line. For BS inoculation, plants were sprayed with a 10⁷ conidia/ml suspension.

Disease severity was assessed every 7 d for ShB and every 10 d for BS from the

Lines derived from *O. officinalis* showing resistance to ShB and BS.

Intensity (0-9 scale)	Lines	
	ShB	BS
1 (highly resistant)	IR54742-6-1-14-15-3 IR54742-33-18-20-3-2 IR54745-2-10-17-8-3 IR54745-2-23-19-8-2 IR54742-1-11-17-12-3	IR54742-1-11-17-26-1 IR54742-1-17-20-8-3 IR54742-33-9-14-26-4 IR54742-33-18-20-3-1 IR54742-33-18-20-3-2 IR54742-38-13-15-11-1 IR54745-2-10-17-8-1 IR54745-2-21-12-17-4 IR54745-2-23-19-8-1 IR54745-2-23-19-18-2
3 (resistant)	IR54742-1-11-17-12-1 IR54742-1-11-17-12-3 IR54742-1-11-17-26-2 IR54742-6-20-3-9-3 IR54742-11-1-9-15-1 IR54742-33-9-14-26-4 IR54745-2-21-12-17-4 IR54745-2-34-3-10-2 IR54751-3-38-10-15-3 IR54742-50-19-19-1-1 IR54742-50-19-19-1-3	IR54742-1-11-17-12-1 IR54742-1-11-17-12-3 IR54742-1-19-11-8-2 IR54742-6-20-3-22-3 IR54742-6-20-9-3-2 IR54742-11-22-2-22-2 IR54742-18-17-20-15-1 IR54742-22-14-24-22-3 IR54742-22-19-3-7-3 IR54742-31-9-26-15-2 IR54742-33-18-20-3-2 IR54745-2-10-17-8-3 IR54745-2-21-12-17-5 IR54745-2-34-3-10-2
9 (highly susceptible)	TKM9 (check)	TKM9

time symptoms appeared on the susceptible check until the milk stage.

Under natural infection, 87 and 48 of the derived lines were ShB- and BS-free.

Under artificial inoculation, 5 lines were highly resistant to ShB and 10 to BS (see table). □

Resistance to sheath rot (ShR) of breeding lines derived from *Oryza officinalis*

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We evaluated 87 breeding lines derived from *O. officinalis* for resistance to ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) W. Gams & Hawksw.

Twenty plants for each derived line were transplanted into 1-row, 3-m-long plots spaced at 30 × 15 cm. Beds were laid out in randomized blocks with three replications. From booting stage onward,